

LARGE DEFLECTION RESPONSE OF SIMPLY SUPPORTED LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO LATERAL TIME DEPENDENT LOADS

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ABSTRACT

A very effective analytical tool for the nonlinear large deflection response of simply supported laminated plates under the action of various types of time dependent lateral loads is presented. The solution, based on the Classical Lamination Theory and accounting for moderately large deflections, is obtained by applying the Galerkin procedure. Several numerical results are presented, including a convergence study, comparisons with other published results, as well as parametric studies. Interesting relations between the load application duration and the lowest plate natural period are drawn out, which can lead to zero response after the load removal.

Keywords : laminated plates; dynamic response; large deflections

1. INTRODUCTION

Considering the loads acting on a marine structure throughout its operational life, we shall hardly find any exhibiting pure static behaviour. The majority of the loading conditions, including the most crucial ones for the integrity of the structure, are characterised by their dynamic nature, which is usually stochastic. A typical example is the slamming phenomenon at the bow of the small fast power boats, as they run with high speeds in rough or moderately rough seas. Analogous conditions are encountered in the aircraft industry, another constructional branch where composite materials are used more and more.

The need for considering nonlinear geometric effects in bending stress analysis under dynamic loads became obvious rather early and, therefore, numerous studies have been realized. An early work on this subject dealt with simply-supported rectangular sandwich plates excited by lateral pulse or sonic boom loadings [1]. Using Classical Lamination Theory (CLT), Mei and Wentz [2] studied analytically the large deflection response of regular antisymmetric angle-ply laminated rectangular plates, simply supported or clamped at all edges. Considering an one-term expansion of the deflection, w , and the stress function, F , and using the Galerkin method they arrived at a nonlinear differential equation with respect to time. The solution was obtained by linearizing this equation. Birman and Bert [3] solved the final differential equation with respect to time by means of the Runge-Kutta numerical integration method. Simply supported boundary conditions were only examined.

A fair amount of finite element studies have also dealt with the problem under consideration. A nine-node rectangular isoparametric shear-deformable finite element was employed by Reddy [4] to investigate the response of isotropic, orthotropic and layered anisotropic composite plates. The same author [5] modified the above element to include the nonlinear strain-displacement relations

of the von Kármán plate theory. A Higher-order Shear Deformation theory was employed by Kant, Ravichandran et al [6] as the basic theory for the development of a shear deformable finite element, to investigate the transient response of laminated composite plates. A detailed review of over 200 references dealing with the geometrically nonlinear behaviour of composite plates has been performed by Chia [7].

The above survey shows the lack of a relatively simple, quick and of acceptable accuracy analytical solution of the dynamic transient response of laminated plates. The existing analytical solutions either do not account for large deflections or, if they do, they seem not to be very accurate, since they incorporate single term expansions of the displacements. In the present study an analytical solution of the bending behaviour of laminated plates of any stacking sequence is given, under the action of various dynamic lateral loads. The solution is based on the CLT (thus, is valid only for thin plates) and accounts for moderately large deflections, since it employs strain-displacement relations in the von Kármán sense. The laminate is considered to be simply supported at its boundaries with stress-free edges at the plane of the plate. Initial out-of-plane imperfections are taken into account, as well as the damping properties of the material.

2. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Governing Equations

Consider a rectangular panel of length a (x -direction), width b (y -direction) and thickness h (z -direction), subjected to an arbitrarily distributed lateral load $q(x,y)$, which, in addition, varies with time. The panel is assumed to consist of any number of composite material layers with different thickness, different material elastic properties and arbitrary fiber orientation angles with respect to the panel geometric axes. Furthermore, let the panel exhibit a steady out-of-plane initial imperfection $w_0(x, y)$, forming any shape and having maximum values in the order of magnitude of the plate thickness.

The derivation of the equations that govern the dynamic flexural behaviour of the laminate under the action of a time dependent lateral load q , is accomplished with the aid of the principle of minimum total potential energy [8]. Introducing the Airy stress function and through proper non-dimensionalisation [9], we obtain the problem's equilibrium and compatibility equations. These two equations are coupled partial differential equations with two dependent variables, the nondimensional total out-of plane deflection W and the nondimensional stress function Φ . Damping is represented as a linear viscous modal damping [10, 11].

There is no classical closed form solution to the above problem and thus, to proceed further in the solution, we employed the Galerkin technique by assuming double sine Fourier series for the nondimensional lateral deflection W and initial imperfection W_0 , with coefficients W_{ij} and W_{0ij} respectively, and the following series for the stress function Φ [9, 12, 13]:

$$\Phi = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Phi_{mn} X_m(\xi) Y_n(\eta) \quad (1)$$

Notice that the initial imperfection of the laminate is assumed to be known and thus the coefficients W_{0ij} are given. The functions X_i and Y_i in the stress function expansion are characteristic beam functions defined as

$$\begin{aligned} X_i(\xi) &= \cosh \alpha_i \xi - \cos \alpha_i \xi - \gamma_i (\sinh \alpha_i \xi - \sin \alpha_i \xi) \\ Y_i(\eta) &= \cosh \alpha_i \eta - \cos \alpha_i \eta - \gamma_i (\sinh \alpha_i \eta - \sin \alpha_i \eta) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

in which α_i and γ_i are constants given in [9, 10]. We furthermore assume that the nondimensional lateral load $\bar{q}(\xi, \eta, \tau)$ can be expanded in a double sine series with coefficients $\bar{q}(\tau)$. For various types of lateral loads, we get:

(a) *Uniform load* $\bar{q}_0(\tau)$ on the entire plate: $\bar{q}_{mn}(\tau) = 16 \bar{q}_0(\tau) / \pi^2 m n$ for m, n odd and 0 for m, n even.

(b) *Sinusoidal load* $\bar{q}(\xi, \eta, \tau) = \bar{q}_0(\tau) \sin(\pi\xi) \sin(\pi\eta)$: $\bar{q}_{mn}(\tau) = \bar{q}_0(\tau)$ for $m=n=1$ and 0 otherwise.

Regarding the time variation of the dimensional applied lateral load $q(t)$, the following commonly encountered forcing-functions are taken into account (see Figure 1):

Figure 1: Various time variations of the applied lateral load q .

virtual displacements are used to include the effect of the unbalanced moments.

Performing all substitutions and integrations in the equilibrium and compatibility equations, a final set of equations is obtained in terms of the coefficients W_{ij} and Φ_{mn} . This set of equations contains an infinite number of nonlinear second order differential and algebraic equations to be solved simultaneously. In practice, only a finite number of these equations will be used to obtain the laminate's bending behaviour to a specified accuracy.

If we consider that all indices vary from 1 to M , that is considering the first M^2 terms of the deflection and the stress function series expansions, the first of the above equations, the equilibrium one, will result in a set of M^2 nonlinear second order differential equations with respect to time, while the second equation, the compatibility one, will give another set of M^2 nonlinear algebraic equations. The general form of these two types of equations is:

a) *Equilibrium Equations*

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d^2 W_{pq}}{d\tau^2} + Z^{pq} \frac{dW_{pq}}{d\tau} + (W_{pq} - W_{opq}) A^{pq} + \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M (W_{ij} - W_{oij}) B_{ij}^{pq} + \\ & + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \Phi_{mn} C_{mn}^{pq} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M \Phi_{mn} W_{ij} D_{mnij}^{pq} + Q^{pq} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$p, q = 1, 2, \dots, M$$

(a) *Suddenly applied constant load (constant pulse):* $q(t) = q_0$ for $t \geq 0$.

(b) *Step loading:* $q(t) = q_0$ for $t \leq t_1$ and 0 otherwise, where t_1 is the duration of the step loading.

(c) *Blast loading:* $q(t) = q_0(1 - t/t_1) \exp(-\alpha t/t_1)$ for $t \leq t_1$ and 0 otherwise, where q_0 is the peak pressure in excess of the ambient pressure, t_1 is the duration of the impulse and α is a coefficient. The values of the blast parameters depend on the distance of the plate from the charge location and are usually taken as $\alpha = 1.98$ and $t_1 = 0.004$ sec [13].

(d) *Half-sine pulse:* $q(t) = q_0 \sin(\pi t/t_1)$ for $t \leq t_1$ and 0 for $t > t_1$, where t_1 is the duration of the pulse.

(e) *Triangular pulse:* $q(t) = 2 q_0 t/t_1$ for $t \leq t_1/2$, $q(t) = 2 q_0 (t_1 - t)/t_1$ for $t_1/2 < t \leq t_1$ and 0 for $t > t_1$, where t_1 is the duration of the pulse.

The above defined functions for W and Φ satisfy simply supported edges free to deform in the plane of the plate (1-2), since U and V are not constant at the boundaries. However, the functions for W and Φ do not satisfy the zero moment condition at the boundaries ($M_\xi = 0$ at $\xi = 0, 1$ and $M_\eta = 0$ at $\eta = 0, 1$) for angle-ply layers and, therefore,

b) *Compatibility Equations*

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \Phi_{mn} H_{mn}^{pq} + \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M (W_{ij} - W_{oij}) K_{ij}^{pq} + \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^M \sum_{t=1}^M (W_{ij} W_{kt} - W_{oij} W_{okt}) L_{ijkt}^{pq} = 0 \tag{4}$$

$$p, q = 1, 2, \dots, M$$

2.2 *Solution Procedure*

Expressing the stress function coefficients Φ_{mn} in terms of the deflection ones W_{mn} , we end up with a set of M^2 coupled nonlinear second order differential equations in terms of W_{mn} only. The general form of the i th of these equations is

$$\frac{d^2 W_i}{d\tau^2} + Z_i \frac{dW_i}{d\tau} = f(\tau, W_1, W_2, \dots, W_{M^2}) \tag{5}$$

subjected to the initial conditions (at $\tau=0$) $W_i=W_{i0}$ and $dW_i/d\tau=0$, signifying that the laminate is at rest before the load application. The above equation describes an initial value problem and is solved by implementing the Runge-Kutta numerical integration scheme.

3. *NUMERICAL RESULTS*

Table 1: Properties of Glass/Epoxy composite.

Young's modulus in direction 1	$E_1=38.6$ GPa
Young's modulus in direction 2	$E_2=8.27$ GPa
Shear modulus	$G_{12}=4.14$ GPa
Poisson ratio	$\nu_{12}=0.260$
Mass density	$\rho=1824$ kg/m ³
Layer thickness	$h_i=0.125$ mm

The laminates are assumed to be formed by alternate layers of a Glass/Epoxy composite, having the material and physical properties of Table 1. The numerical study was performed using the Runge-Kutta adaptive step integrator, as the most efficient integration tool. This

decision was based on a thorough investigation of various alternative numerical schemes [8].

3.1 *Convergence Study*

A convergence study was performed to obtain the minimum required number of the deflection

Figure 2: W_c time history of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate ($a/b=2.0$) - constant pulse ($q_0=25$ Pa).

W and stress function Φ series terms for an adequate representation of these two magnitudes, when the lateral load is uniformly distributed over the laminate area. In Figure 2 the center deflection W_c versus time of a rectangular ($a=50$ cm, $b=25$ mm, $h=1$ mm) ACP (antisymmetric cross-ply) $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate has been plotted, for a one, nine and twenty five series terms approximation. The considered load is a constant pulse with a maximum value of $q_0=25$ Pa, whereas damping effects have been neglected. On the basis of this and numerous other runs, the nine terms approximation seems to give quite accurate results for the deflection of a laminate under a uniform spatial distribution of the lateral load and, thus,

Figure 3: W_c time history of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate ($a/b=2.0$) - constant pulse ($q_0 = 1$ Pa).

mean value (the static solution), with a somewhat constant frequency. The non-harmonic nature of this periodic motion is exhibited by the asymmetry of the parts of each oscillation corresponding to

Figure 4: Fourier Transform of the W_c time history of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate ($a/b=2.0$) - constant pulse ($q_0 = 1.0$ Pa).

Figure 5: Fourier Transform of the W_c time history of a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate ($a/b=2.0$) - constant pulse ($q_0 = 25.0$ Pa).

the first and the second semiperiod intervals, as well as from the negative values of the deflection W for time values which are selected multiples of the period of oscillation.

To better understand and explain these particular characteristics, we have calculated the response of the same laminate in the linear phase, under a small magnitude constant pulse of $q_0 = 1$ Pa. The results are shown in Figure 3, both for the total, as well as for the constituent deflection terms. Note that, since the laminate is orthotropic and not square ($a/b=2.0$), term W_{31} dominates over terms W_{13} and W_{33} which are negligibly small. The Fourier Transform of the deflection time history shown in Figures 3 ($q_0 = 1$ Pa, linear phase) and 2 ($q_0 = 25$ Pa, nonlinear phase) is shown in Figures 4 and 5 respectively. The first four natural frequencies of the laminate were calculated to be 29.412, 44.121, 73.695 and 106.804 Hz, corresponding to mode shapes (2,1), (2,3), (2,2) and (3,1) respectively. Comparing the frequencies of the harmonic constituents of the deflection time histories with the laminate's natural frequencies, it becomes evident from Fig. 4 that, in the linear phase, the laminate oscillates with a fundamental frequency equal to its first natural frequency and with a superharmonic equal to its third frequency of free vibrations. Both these magnitudes are shifted to greater values for the nonlinear case of Figure 5. Similar results were found in extensive numerical studies for other types of laminates, as well as for isotropic plates [8].

3.2 Comparison of Results

Results obtained by the present methodology have been compared with the ones of Bhimaraddi [15], for square plates under the action of a sinusoidally distributed constant pulse. Bhimaraddi proposed a First-order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT) to study the linear transient response of

all the following numerical results have been obtained with this number of series terms. Nevertheless, this is not the case for the calculated stresses, since convergence has not been attained even for a forty nine series terms ($M=7$) approximation. This is attributed to the fact that stresses are expressed in terms of the second derivatives of the deflection and stress function, thus not showing the same general behaviour. A further increase in the number of series terms leads to unacceptably high computer costs.

A closer look at the results of Figure 2 indicates that after the instantaneous application of the load, the laminate deflection increases up to some level (depending on the laminate stiffness), and then oscillates about a

Figure 6: W_c time history of a square orthotropic plate - uniformly distributed blast loading.

uniformly distributed over the plate surface and applied as a blast load. The results are shown in Figure 6. The plate's more stiff consideration made by the ADINA modelling, results, as expected, to smaller peak deflection values, and to an oscillating motion of higher frequency than the one arising from the analytical method. The frequency difference has the expected consequence of a phase shift of the ADINA results with respect to the others. However, the peak differences are not unacceptably high, being about 10%, something which, along with the fact that the analytical solution gives conservative results, leads to the conclusion that the present method can be used as a design tool. Regarding time step effects, it can be said that the value of 0.5 msec is adequate for the present case, but great care must be given to the time step selection, if large time intervals are to be integrated.

3.3 Parametric Study

Our attention will be first focused on the effect of the various types of time dependent loads on the nonlinear response of laminates. This response under three different types of load, is shown in Figure 7. The lateral load is uniformly distributed and the laminate is a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ cross-ply one with $a=50$ cm, $b=25$ cm, $h=1$ mm and material properties the ones of Table 1. The load maximum value is $q_0=60$ Pa and the duration of the step pulse and the blast loading is $t_1=0.05$ sec. The solutions corresponding to the constant and the step pulse go together up to the neighbourhood of 0.05 sec (phase I), where the application of the step pulse ends. This is an expected feature, since at this time

Figure 7: W_c time history for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4$ laminate - various types of uniform lateral pressure.

interval the two loads are identical. The motion is an oscillation, having a mean value near the static solution deflection ($w_c/h=1.33$). After $t=0.05$ sec (phase II), the constant pulse response continues its oscillations as previously, while the step load response begins a new oscillating motion around the zero deflection value, having a greater amplitude than previously. As it will be shown later, this amplitude of phase II free vibration motion can be less or more than the phase I one, or even zero, depending on the relation between the pulse duration t_1 and the first natural period of the plate T . Differing from the other two, the blast loading response is an oscillating motion around a

laminated plates, and he obtained the CLT solution as a limited case of his theory. It was concluded that the present method correlates well with the CLT solution of Bhimaraddi.

The finite element computer code ADINA [16] was also used for comparison purposes. Three-node flat triangular plate/shell elements with six DOF per node were used, with 144 elements in one quarter of the plate. The effect of the magnitude of the time step was investigated by performing the calculations with three time steps, namely $\Delta t=4$, $\Delta t=2$ and $\Delta t=0.5$ msec. The comparison was made for a square orthotropic plate with $a=b=50$ cm, $h=1$ mm, and having the material properties of Table 1. The lateral load was

decreasing mean value, which becomes zero at $t=0.05$ sec. After that time (phase II), a free vibration motion begins around zero deflection. The rate of increase, as well as the peak values of deflection caused by the blast loading are smaller than the ones generated by the constant or the step pulse, since, for the same time interval, the energy passed to the plate by the blast load is less than the corresponding one given by the pulse. Therefore, in general, blast loadings produce smaller maximum deflections than constant or step pulses.

The step pulse response behaviour at phase II (the free vibration motion) depends on the relative magnitudes of the step duration t_1 and the laminate's first natural period of free vibrations T , being in straight relation with the corresponding behaviour of a spring-mass single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) system.

It can be readily proven that a zero deflection and velocity condition at $t=t_1$ is obtained when t_1 is an integer multiple of the system's natural period T and, therefore,

$$x_{II} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad t_1 = nT, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (6)$$

This period is the one corresponding to the degree of the motion nonlinearity and is not the one calculated by the linear eigenvalue problem.

Seeking relations analogous to the ones of Equation (6) between the pulse duration t_1 and the first natural period T in order for the phase II oscillating motion to vanish, we refer once more to the SDOF system. For the case of a sine pulse of intensity p_0 and duration t_1 , in order for the motion at phase II to vanish, the following condition must hold:

$$x_{II} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad t_1 = (2n + 1)T/2 \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (7)$$

In the case of a triangular pulse of peak value p_0 and duration t_1 , the corresponding condition is

$$x_{II} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad t_1 = 2nT \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (8)$$

The effect of damping is investigated in Figure 8 for a $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_4$ glass/epoxy cross-ply laminate with $a=50$ cm, $b=25$ cm, $h=1$ mm and having the material properties of Table 1. The laminate is subjected to a sinusoidally distributed constant pulse of intensity $q_0=60$ Pa. Information about damping characteristics and properties of composite materials are rarely presented in the literature. A lot of experimental study has yet to be made in this field for a better understanding of the phenomenon, as well as for the collection of a fair amount of damping properties data. The damping ratio $\zeta (=c/c_c)$ has been reported to range between 0.005 and 0.05 for the common type of composites used in aircraft structures [2]. Results for four different values of the damping ratio ζ are presented in Figure 8. All results finally converge to the static solution $w_c/h=0.92$, as expected.

Figure 8: W_c time history for a $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_4$ laminate - constant pulse, for various damping ratios.

4. CONCLUSIONS

An analytic tool was presented in this paper for the nonlinear static and dynamic response calculation of simply supported composite laminated plates under the action of lateral loads. The laminate can have any stacking sequence, whereas its edges were assumed to be stress-free, modelling that way the less stiff possible configuration of a simply supported plate. The results of the present method are conservative with respect to any other type of boundary conditions, thus constituting an upper limit for all possible configurations.

An extensive parametric study was carried out revealing that the undamped response of a laminate under a constant

pulse load is an oscillating motion with fundamental frequency near its lowest natural frequency. This fundamental frequency increases slightly with increasing degree of nonlinearity.

Referring to the various types of load time variations, the maximum deflection peak values are produced by the constant and the step loading, while the minimum ones by the triangular pulse, when the load maximum value and pulse duration are the same. For the step, sine and triangular pulses, special relations between the duration of load application and the lowest plate natural period, result in very small deflections after the removal of the load. This characteristic can be very significant in designing structures which are subjected frequently to pulse loads, since, with a proper material and geometry configuration selection, fatigue problems can be minimized. Furthermore, special attention must be given to the fact that maximum deflections may occur even after the load removal, during the free oscillation phase of the plate, and, therefore, proper consideration must be made when selecting the time interval for our calculations.

A further development of the method should incorporate deflection and stress function series expansions capable of modelling more types of boundary conditions, and resulting in faster convergence for the stress calculations. An extensive experimental verification of the results presented here is considered to be necessary, as it will help to acquire more confidence for the special characteristics revealed here.

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